

Implementation of the Defense and Security of the Universal People in Preventing the Spread and Abuse of Narcotics as a Non-military Threat in West Kalimantan

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Abstract: *The threat of the danger of spreading and abusing narcotics is one of the non-military threats in West Kalimantan that can cause harm to society and the state. This study aims to analyze the implementation of universal people's defense and security in an effort to prevent the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan as a non-military threat. This study uses a qualitative research method with a descriptive analytical approach. The results of this study are cooperation in the management of West Kalimantan human resources in an effort to prevent the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan as a non-military threat which is carried out through, improving the quality of human resources by planning, organizing, mobilizing, and controlling which also involves the role of various agencies in Kalimantan. West. Coordination and communication are also carried out well between the BNNP of West Kalimantan with the TNI AD, Polri in carrying out joint patrols on a scheduled basis as one of the efforts to prevent the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan.*

Keywords: BNNP, Cooperation, Dayak Customary Council, Narcotics Abuse, Non-military Threats, Police, Synergy West Kalimantan, TNI.

I. INTRODUCTION

The dynamics of the development of the strategic environment today has an impact on the patterns and dynamics of threats that are increasingly complex and multidimensional. These threats can be in the form of military, non-military threats or a combination of both, namely hybrid threats. These threats are grouped into real and unreal threats. The forms of these threats are the threat of terrorism, separatism, armed rebellion, natural disasters, territorial violations, piracy, natural resource theft, cyber attacks, drug trafficking and abuse. These threats lead to issues on ideological, political, economic, socio-cultural and security factors. Threats can come from international, regional and national carried out by state actors and non-state actors (Indonesian Defense White Paper, 2015). The current regional conditions is still dominated by several issues of actual threats which include border conflicts and various cross-border crimes, one of which is drug smuggling (Alfajri, 2019).

The threat of spreading and abusing narcotics is classified as a non-military threat because it can interfere with national security in cultural, social and economic dimensions. Distribution and abuse of narcotics in Indonesia is a problem that is currently a concern for the government. Narcotics abuse that is not in accordance with its designation can have a domino effect and can damage the mental and morale of the nation. From the data released by the National Narcotics Agency in 2020, the number of drug crime cases throughout Indonesia reached 40,756 cases (Indonesian Drugs Report BNN, 2020). Drug abuse is related to economic law where demand and supply apply, the demand for illegal drugs in Indonesia is still relatively high, resulting in high supply coming from outside and from within the country.

Based on data released by the Regional Police (Polda) of West Kalimantan, throughout 2020, 760 drug cases have been revealed with a total of 54.9 kilograms of crystal methamphetamine, 11.5 kilograms of marijuana and 19,500 ecstasy pills. Table 1. Recapitulation of Drug Cases in Kalimantan in 2019-2020.

Province	2019 (case)	2020 (case)
West Kalimantan	728	760
South Kalimantan	1.747	1.579
Central Kalimantan	657	625
East Kalimantan	1.686	1.355
North Kalimantan	22	10

Source: Regional Police in Kalimantan Island

West Kalimantan has an area of 146,807 km², which is directly bordered by Malaysia and the South China Sea. In the north, West Kalimantan is bordered by Sarawak, East Malaysia. Meanwhile, in the west, it is directly facing the South China Sea and the Natuna Sea. This geographical condition makes West Kalimantan vulnerable to become a route for narcotics smuggling from other countries. Recorded by the West Kalimantan Regional Police, West Kalimantan has 52 rat trails that are often used by illegal immigrants to enter and exit the borders of Indonesia and Malaysia. In addition to land, smuggling also occurs by sea and air. Drug smuggling by sea in West Kalimantan is very prone to occur because of the many unofficial ports and without any safeguards. The Governor of West Kalimantan, Sutarmidji, in the Domestic Work Lecture held by the Defense Management Faculty of the Defense University stated that more than 90% of drug cases in West Kalimantan originate from Malaysia by land, water and air. The extent of the border area makes drug smugglers still free to enter and exit through rat roads without the supervision of officers from the Army and Police.

The case of narcotics smuggling and abuse that occurred in West Kalimantan is one example of a non-military threat that has become a national issue and must receive more attention from the central government, related agencies and also local governments. Efforts to deal with non-military threats place Ministries/Institutions (K/L) in accordance with their fields which are placed as the main elements of defense supported by other elements of the nation's power, this is stated in Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning National Defense. From this policy, it can be seen that the BNN of West Kalimantan Province is the main element in preventing the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan with the support of other elements, namely the TNI, Polri and also the Regional Government.

Based on Law Number 35 of 2009 concerning Narcotics, the task of the BNN of West Kalimantan Province is to carry out the duties and functions as well as the authority of the National Narcotics Agency within the province of West Kalimantan. These tasks include making policies, work programs, regulating cooperation with government and non-government agencies, the TNI and Polri.

In its duties and functions, the West Kalimantan BNNP requires synergistic cooperation with stakeholders who are also related to the West Kalimantan BNNP work program. The course of synergy that occurs between related agencies is influenced by external and internal factors (Priyadi, 2015). Internal factors, among others, relate to how the human resources in the work team are managed and formed, then the facilities that support cooperation, and adequate infrastructure. Cooperation relationships with other agencies also require a memorandum of understanding or MoU to align goals. External factors that support the occurrence of a collaboration, for example, are the support for the development of information technology for the process of socializing the work program of the West Kalimantan BNNP and assisting the West Kalimantan BNNP with relevant agencies in conducting investigations.

The threat of drug danger which is a non-military threat must be placed as a fundamental concern of the central government, ministries/agencies and also local governments because the threat of drug abuse can weaken the moral and mentality of the Indonesian nation. In defense efforts to deal with non-military threats, support between Ministries/Institutions outside the defense sector is needed in order to increase the strength of the nation by increasing synergies. In dealing with the threat of drugs, the West Kalimantan BNNP is placed as the main element supported by other ministries/agencies according to their duties and functions such as the TNI, Polri and the West Kalimantan Customary Council. As another element of the nation's strength, in supporting Ministries/Agencies to face non-military threats, the TNI has been prepared in an integrated manner as stated in the RI Law no. 34 of 2004 concerning the TNI. It is stated in Law No. 34 of 2004 that the TNI in carrying out its duties is carried out through War Military Operations (OMP) and also (OMSP) Military Operations Other than War. There are 14 tasks of OMSP, one of which is to assist Ministries/Agencies in securing against smuggling.

Furthermore, the National Police at the Regional level or later called Polda, has a drug unit whose task is to carry out investigations and investigations of criminal acts of drug abuse, counseling and coaching in the context of preventing and rehabilitating victims of drug abuse.

The role of the Customary Council is no less important in dealing with the threat of drug distribution and abuse in West Kalimantan. Through traditional leaders coordinated by the Customary Council, they will be able to socialize the dangers of narcotics and become supervisors in a community group. The Customary Council also plays a role in developing local wisdom in the form of community forums in order to prevent the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan.

Communication and coordination are one of the factors that influence a collaboration and encourage a synergistic collaboration to be able to run optimally. Cooperation between Ministries/Agencies is very much needed to encourage the handling of non-military threats to be more effective and efficient. Coordination and communication are also needed in order to form synergistic cooperation between government and non-government Ministries/Institutions in West Kalimantan so that it is expected to produce a defense force that has high deterrence in West Kalimantan in preventing smuggling and drug abuse as a non-military threat.

In this study, the theory used is the theory of defense management and the concept of Defense and Security of the Universal People. The theoretical basis used in research is to become an arrangement of concepts that have variables in research. Sugiyono (2019) also explained that the theoretical basis is a flow of logic or reasoning which is a set of concepts, definitions, and proportions that are systematically arranged.

The basis of defense management theory is aimed at achieving the expected goals. Defense management is a process to make policies into something that can be implemented (Supriyatno, 2014). The basic concepts of Defense Management are broadly functional in line with the concept of Management itself, namely planning, organizing, actuating, coordinating and controlling. Management is described in the Republic of Indonesia Law Number 3 of 2002 concerning National Defense and Law Number 34 of 2004, which explains that "the management of national defense is all activities at the strategic and policy level which include planning, implementation, supervision, and control of national defense.". Defense Management functions to combine available resources within the state defense organization with training, with good equipment and support in order to complete the goals and missions that have been planned and determined (Supriyatno, 2014).

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative research method with a descriptive analytical approach. Creswell (2016) states that qualitative research will build meaning about a phenomenon based on the views or opinions of the informants. Qualitative methods can be used to describe, summarize various conditions, situations or reveal and understand something behind a phenomenon that is not at all known. According to Sugiono (2016), the analytical descriptive approach is a method that serves to describe or provide an overview of the object under study through data or samples that have been collected as they are then analyze and draw conclusions that apply to the public.

Data collection is a systematic procedure for collecting data needed in a study. This study uses interview and documentation data collection techniques. The in-depth interview method is carried out with the intention of collecting primary data or information directly from sources. The documentation method is carried out to obtain data by utilizing secondary data that is already available or processed. This secondary data is obtained from sources relevant to the problem, through literature studies in the form of official documents of government organizations and other institutional documents, transcripts, books, newspapers, magazines, agendas, archives, and other libraries.

Based on the description that has been disclosed, the researcher uses a qualitative research method with a descriptive analytical approach to analyze more deeply the implementation of the Defense and Security of the People of the Universe in an effort to prevent the spread and abuse of narcotics as a non-military threat in West Kalimantan.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The Concept of Defense and Security of the Universal People (Hankamrata)

Security is what every citizen needs to be able to live and socialize in it. National security is essentially the realization of a sense of security and peace in living life in a country. In maintaining and protecting the security of the nation and state, based on the 1945 Constitution Article 30 paragraph 2 states that national defense is carried out using a Universal People's Defense and Security System (Sishankamrata).

The concept of Defense and Security of the People of the Universe (Hankamrata) is essentially an effort to defend the country from all threats by involving all components of the state, including the community and national power in it. This is in accordance with what is stated in the 1945 Constitution Article 30 Paragraph 1 which reads "Every citizen has the right and is obliged to participate in efforts to defend the state". National defense efforts do not only ward off military threats, but also non-military threats.

In dealing with non-military threats in all dimensions and types of threats, the government also prepares the necessary capabilities early, and implements them in a total, integrated, and directed manner in accordance with the values of the Defense and Security Doctrine, namely populist, regional and universal.

All forms of threats must be anticipated for the purpose of preparing for prevention, action / overcoming, mitigation and restoration of the impact of damage caused by non-military threats. The management and implementation of Universal People's Defense and Security in the face of non-military threats requires effective collaboration and coordination between the Main Elements and Other Elements which can be realized in the form of legal instruments, Standard Operation Procedures (SOP), mutual agreements, or other forms of initiatives.

3.2 Conditions of Distribution and Abuse of Narcotics in West Kalimantan

The problem of narcotics abuse in Indonesia is currently a national problem that almost every region in Indonesia has. The current state of the Covid-19 pandemic has made drug abuse even more vulnerable. People who are stressed due to the pandemic due to losing their jobs will be used by drug dealers to get involved in drug abuse because many people have lost their jobs or livelihoods. Prof. dr. Soewadi in a webinar held by the Islamic University of Indonesia in collaboration with BNN, assessed drug abuse as an iceberg phenomenon. This means that the number of people who use drugs that is visible on the surface is smaller than the number of people who are hidden.

West Kalimantan Province has a geographical location which is directly adjacent to Malaysia in the north. West Kalimantan has many illegal land routes along the border. This condition makes West Kalimantan vulnerable to drug smuggling and transactions from foreign countries. The borders are through Entikong, JagoiBabangBengkayang, Aruk Sambas, Kapuas Hulu and Sintang.

Data released by the National Narcotics Agency of West Kalimantan Province states that the international circulation of narcotics entering Indonesia is mostly through land routes, especially the West Kalimantan region. The current international narcotics network continues to look for gaps and opportunities to enter by establishing Indonesia as a potential market share and continues to grow (Gafar, 2012).

3.3 Implementation of Hankamrata in Dealing with the Spread and Abuse of Narcotics in West Kalimantan

3.3.1 The Role of the National Narcotics Agency of West Kalimantan Province (BNNP)

The phenomenon of drug abuse is now increasingly permeating the joints of people's lives. The target consumers are getting younger in terms of age, the more varied the modus operandi and the more massive the circulation. Currently, almost all levels of society are capable of being penetrated by this narcotics network. Therefore, attention and cooperation between various government agencies is needed to overcome it.

In dealing with the circulation of narcotics and narcotics abuse from within the country and abroad, the Government of Indonesia has formed a body called the National Narcotics Agency (BNN). The formation of the National Narcotics Agency (BNN) itself is based on the legal basis that has been established in the Presidential Decree of the Republic of Indonesia No. 17 of 2002 which was later replaced by Presidential Regulation No. 83 of 2007 and revised again by Presidential Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 23 of 2010 concerning Agency National Narcotics.

The National Narcotics Agency (BNN) itself is a non-structural institution located under and directly responsible to the President, which only has the task and function of coordinating. The National Narcotics Agency (BNN) has representatives in the provinces and districts/cities as vertical agencies, namely the BNNP (Provincial National Narcotics Agency) and district/city BNN.

Strategies for dealing with drug problems by developing an intensive community self-defense system through promotive efforts and developing life skills from an early age; develop an early detection system for drug abuse in the family, education, work, and community environment; optimizing the participation of government agencies, the private sector, community organizations (religious, women, youth, professions, etc.) in the massive anti-drug campaign; develop rehabilitation services for drug addicts in an integrated and sustainable manner; strengthening the interdiction system in the area of entry routes (sea ports, airports, and land routes); reveal the network of drug crimes to completion; confiscate the assets of drug syndicates originating from drug crimes; improve coordination and cooperation across agencies and across countries in the context of disclosing drug crime syndicates; encourage the execution of death row convicts for drug cases to provide a deterrent effect.

In order to carry out activities or efforts to abuse narcotics, the West Kalimantan BNNP prioritizes coordination in districts that have a BNNK and encourages BNNP as a function builder in order to maximize performance in the field. It can take the form of coordination and cooperation, whether it's a work meeting or a work visit. then BNNP West Kalimantan also hears or advocates for policy making in the region to be able to support existing activities. The West Kalimantan BNNP is tasked with synchronizing how to cooperate in existing activities at BNNK and BNNP as

well as in the Region. After synchronizing and synergizing, we can take action together, whether it is sharing activities or funds. This collaboration is carried out in the context of synergy with regions where there is no BNNK in the context of P4GN synchronizing and jointly implementing P4GN activities in the regions. Currently in West Kalimantan, out of 14 regencies, 7 still have BNNKs.

The dangers of drugs cannot only be handled by the government but require cooperation from various levels of society (Kurniawan, 2020). Another West Kalimantan BNNP program is recruiting anti-drug volunteers. Members of the anti-drug volunteer are absorbed from the general public, students and from other agencies. Anti-drug volunteers are given education as well as workshops and seminars on the basics of the dangers of drugs to the community.

The West Kalimantan BNNP also coordinates regularly with the Indonesian Army, which is very aggressive in conducting patrols to prevent smuggling and distribution of narcotics at the border. Patrols are carried out every day together with the TNI AD on a scheduled basis, one of which is by using patrol aircraft that can detect quickly if there are violations at border points. Coordination and communication between the BNNP of West Kalimantan and the TNI AD is carried out well so as to increase efforts to prevent the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan.

The coordination carried out by the West Kalimantan BNNP with the Indonesian Army in an effort to prevent smuggling, distribution and abuse in West Kalimantan is in designing collaborative programs or activities ranging from planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating in order to overcome the dangers of spreading and abusing narcotics in West Kalimantan. through the preparation of planning documents both annual (Work Plan) and intermediate (Strategic Plan).

In addition to increasing human resources internally, the West Kalimantan BNNP also makes efforts to prevent the spread and abuse of narcotics by improving the quality of community human resources, namely by establishing Anti-Drug Volunteers consisting of students, community leaders, government and general government officials, and the general public. Anti-Drug Volunteer members are given education and briefing about the dangers of drugs to the community and how to communicate so that later can be communicated to the community. Efforts to increase community human resources also involve the role of the Indonesian Army.

3.3.2 The Role of the Indonesian National Army

The Indonesian National Army (TNI) has the duty and function to maintain and uphold the nation's sovereignty, defend the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia and also protect the entire nation and the homeland of Indonesia from all threats, challenges, obstacles and disturbances to the integrity of the nation and state. The TNI as a defense tool has the task of carrying out military operations for war and military operations other than war, this is stated in Law Number 34 of 2004 concerning the Indonesian National Army. Article 7 paragraph 2 point (b) of Law Number 34 of 2004 states that the task of military operations other than war is to secure border areas.

The border area of a country is part of the country's territory which is located on the inside along the border of the Indonesian state with other countries, the border area is in the sub-district area in terms of the country's territorial boundaries on land. The border area is the door of a country, where many Indonesian citizens and foreign countries enter Indonesia. Every Indonesian citizen and foreign citizen who comes to Indonesia has their own interests. In addition to maintaining the sovereignty of the country's territory, the TNI is tasked with preventing smuggling and illegal acts around the border, including those related to narcotics.

The result of the synergy between the West Kalimantan BNNP and the Pamantas Battalion 642/Kps task force was the success of securing 40 packages of crystal methamphetamine during border patrols, the information of which was known to the intelligence task force team and the West Kalimantan BNNP. The smuggling took place on an illegal route in the Hamlet of Aruk, Sebunga Village, Sajingan Besar District, Sambas Regency, West Kalimantan. The Head of the Eradication Division of the BNNP West Kalimantan stated that the drugs were made in China which transited in Malaysia and would then be distributed to Indonesia via West Kalimantan.

According to the Head of BNNP West Kalimantan, synergy with the Indonesian Army is also established in efforts to prevent narcotics smuggling through illegal routes at the border in West Kalimantan with Malaysia. In human resource management, BNNP West Kalimantan has improved HR through improving the quality of the internal HR of BNNP West Kalimantan, which consists of: a) planning, namely compiling an analysis of employee needs; b) organizing, namely mapping positions based on education and compiling workload analysis and employee formation; c) mobilization, namely monitoring, evaluating and controlling the implementation of activities, monitoring and making policies through coordination meetings; d) control, namely electronic attendance, as well as other inherent supervision according to the level of position, while in the field it is led by a team commander who has been equipped with communication tools to be able to coordinate with other agencies, such as the Indonesian Army.

TNI cooperation with BNNP West Kalimantan in dealing with the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan is established in a communication and coordination. With the limited number of investigators from the West Kalimantan BNNP, BNNP coordinates with the Indonesian Army Pamantas Task Force to maximize the performance of the available personnel. This is done by means of good management and organization.

3.3.3 The Role of the Regional Police of West Kalimantan

Narcotics abuse in Indonesia has reached a very worrying stage. Narcotics no longer recognize age limits, old people, young people, teenagers and even children are users and dealers of narcotics. The circulation of illegal narcotics in Indonesia is no less worrying, drugs are not only circulating in big cities in Indonesia, but also have penetrated to the regions.

West Kalimantan, which used to be a transit area or traffic for illicit narcotics trade due to the very strategic geographical location of West Kalimantan Province, has turned into a province that has the potential to spread and abuse Narcotics. This can be seen by the disclosure of several cases of smuggling and narcotics abuse that the West Kalimantan Regional Police have successfully uncovered every year (West Kalimantan Regional Police Data 2018-2020).

Drug prevention and eradication efforts can be carried out by the West Kalimantan Regional Police in three ways, namely pre-emptive efforts, preventive efforts (prevention), and repressive efforts (actions). These three things are the main (operational) functions in accordance with the main tasks of the National Police as regulated in Article 13 of the Police Law, namely:

a) Pre-Emptive Efforts (coaching)

Pre-emptive efforts here are the initial efforts made by the police to prevent criminal acts from occurring. Efforts have been made to prevent crime pre-emptively by holding outreach hearings about the dangers of drugs to the community, students, religious leaders and community leaders, as well as the West Kalimantan Regional Police in cooperation (MoU) on drug prevention with related agencies, schools, universities, religious groups, and community groups.

b) Preventive Efforts (prevention)

Preventive efforts are a follow-up to Pre-Emptive efforts, which are still at the level of prevention before the occurrence of a crime. In preventive efforts, the emphasis is on eliminating opportunities to commit crimes. Preventive efforts (prevention) are intended as efforts to make positive changes to the possibility of disturbances in society, so as to create legal stability. The efforts made by the West Kalimantan Regional Police in this preventive effort are as follows:

- 1) Carry out patrols to areas suspected of being a place for illicit drug abuse
- 2) Conduct raids in places such as cafes, karaoke, and nightclubs
- 3) Conduct a campaign to stop illicit trafficking and drug abuse
- 4) Installing a banner or banner that says about the dangers of drugs
- 5) Calling on the public to report if there are families who become drug addicts for further treatment and rehabilitation.

c) Repressive Efforts

Repressive efforts are conceptual efforts to overcome crime which are taken after the crime has occurred. Countermeasures with repressive measures are intended to take action against the perpetrators of crimes according to their actions and correct them again so that they are aware that their actions are unlawful and detrimental to society, so they will not repeat it and other people will not do it, considering the sanctions that will be borne are very heavy. . In addition to Law Number 2 of 2002 concerning the Indonesian National Police. The police are also tasked with carrying out investigations and investigations as regulated in Law No. 81 of 1981. Investigations and investigations are different things. An investigation is a series of actions as investigators to seek and find an event that is suspected of being a criminal act in order to determine whether or not an investigation can be carried out according to the method regulated in the Act (Soesilo, 1997).

3.3.4 The Role of the West Kalimantan Dayak Customary Council (DAD West Kalimantan)

West Kalimantan is a province in Indonesia located on the island of Kalimantan, with the capital city or government center in the city of Pontianak. West Kalimantan is the fourth largest province in Indonesia after Papua, East Kalimantan and Central Kalimantan.

The majority of the indigenous population is inhabited by Dayak, and various immigrant tribes. West Kalimantan can be said to be the mediator of Indonesia because all ethnicities and religions exist in West Kalimantan, which is the uniqueness of West Kalimantan.

Various ethnic groups in West Kalimantan (22 ethnicities) live side by side. This creates various social problems and is prone to conflict. The impact of the 1997 conflict caused economic and social difficulties. DAD was founded because of the conflict that occurred in 1997. The highest Dayak Customary Council (DAD) at the provincial level headed by the President. Then at the Regency/City level, there are 12 Regency DADs and 2 City DADs.

The vision of DAD is as an institution that is able to increase the dignity of the Dayak Indigenous Peoples in the era of globalization by encouraging positive values of the Dayak Indigenous People's life as part of the life of the nation and state. DAD also contributes in managing the life of the Dayak Indigenous people towards change based on dignity through a sustainable empowerment process that is democratic, transparent, participatory, accountable, and transformative. This is done with the aim of maintaining a balance in the various dimensions of the life of the Dayak Indigenous People with the creator, the environment and fellow human beings.

Efforts made by the West Kalimantan DAD in dealing with the threat of the spread and misuse of Narcotics in West Kalimantan are to conduct Coordination Meetings with other Ministries and Institutions, such as the National Narcotics Agency of West Kalimantan Province, the regional police, and also the West Kalimantan regional government. In addition, DAD also actively coordinates with the Regional Leadership Coordination Forum with the aim of improving the quality of human resources by inviting tribal chiefs to be given socialization about the threat of narcotics.

IV. CONCLUSION

Cooperation in dealing with the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan as a non-military threat has been carried out by various Ministries/Agencies in West Kalimantan through planning, organizing, mobilizing, and controlling which also involves the roles of BNNP, TNI, Polri and the West Kalimantan Dayak Customary Council. One form of Defense and Security of the People of the Universe in dealing with the threat of the spread and abuse of narcotics is to improve the quality of community human resources through programs or activities that also involve the role of BNNP, TNI, Polri and the West Kalimantan Dayak Customary Council.

Improving the quality of human resources is carried out with the aim that the public has insight into the dangers of the threat of spreading and abusing narcotics for the community and the state. In addition, coordination and communication are also carried out well between the BNNP of West Kalimantan with the TNI, Polri and the Dayak Customary Council in carrying out joint patrols on a scheduled basis as one of the efforts to prevent the spread and abuse of narcotics in West Kalimantan.

In general, the implementation of the Universal People's Defense and Security in dealing with the threat of the spread and abuse of narcotics in the West Kalimantan area has been carried out in accordance with the 1945 Constitution. Each Ministry and Institution has contributed by carrying out their duties in accordance with their role in preventing and dealing with the threat of the spread and abuse of narcotics in the West Kalimantan Region.

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